

1999 New Zealand Microbiological Society Conference (Nov 24th to Nov 26th)

To Lyal French-Wright, Principal

The sessions began at 8:30am and usually finished at around 5:30pm with the usual breaks for tea and lunch. Jared did not seem to notice that the day was longer than he would have at school. He seemed interested in everything that was going on and was keen to attend sessions that included topics that will be covered in School Certificate such as biotechnology, disease organisms, and the environment.

The response from former colleagues and scientists representing NZMS as a whole was tremendous. Conference convener Dr Greg Cook (University of Otago) said in the Otago Daily News (attached) that the work we presented was brilliant. Jared was the youngest person to present research at a conference. In conversation society president Dr Gillian Lewis (Auckland University) said she expected to see us at the special 2000 joint Australia NZ conference in Cairns next year. She has offered an opportunity for Nexus to present an oral paper, extraordinary in that oral papers are by invitation only, reserved for guest speakers or post-grad research students.

Dr Chris Harfoot (Waikato University) said many of the researchers present were stunned and excited to see High School students working at this level. The volunteer work by two experienced scientists (namely Christine and myself), one also a trained and experienced teacher and a member of the NZMS was a golden opportunity for society. To this end, at the AGM held Thursday evening, the efforts of the NPBHS students was discussed. Various Government facilities and Tertiary Institutions are willing to look at NPBHS as a pilot school for developing experiments, guides and multimedia resources that will go into every school in New Zealand. We would be named as co-authors. The various trade exhibitors gave an undertaking to provide a research microscope and other consumable items for joint development and publication of teaching resources.

To help promote our achievements and establish further links in the scientific community, the NZMS would like us to prepare an article for their newsletter. This will ultimately allow us to place students over the holidays in labs for work experience or in helping make careers choices. If nothing else, it will also make the material in class texts seem more real for the student.

In summary:

NPBHS has two recognised research publications based on the work of our students.
Our Form Four student is the youngest person to present research at a conference
We have an invitation to present an oral paper in Australia next year (June)
We could be a pilot school with co-authorship on resource kits, teachers notes, multi-media resources.
We have offers of equipment and consumable material from various biotechnology firms
Various University labs will pass on lab gear if we can collect it (school van?)
Excellent chance of continuing publicity in the press for the NPBHS as further NEXUS research findings come to light.

For this to happen, adequate release from class contact next year must be provided.

Thankyou for assisting us in attending this conference. Jared was indeed an excellent ambassador for the school. We have the attention of a powerful professional body. The NZMS could help NPBHS establish a niche in education that no-one else in New Zealand has thought of.

Michael Fenton M.Sc., Dip.Tchg.
Nexus Research Group Founder/Director
Science Teacher
New Plymouth Boy's High School